

Variable Kinematics enabled by Layer Jamming Transition in a Soft Bending Actuator

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Abstract—In soft robotics, variable stiffness is typically employed to solve the trade-off between compliance and the ability to exert high forces. However, modulating the stiffness of a soft actuator can also provide control over its deformation and enhance its adaptability. This latter concept has not been thoroughly investigated in literature and this work aims at demonstrating variable kinematics enabled by the integration of variable stiffness modules into the structure of a soft finger. We have augmented a segmented pneumatic bending actuator with two-layer jamming modules integrated into its proximal and distal sections and proposed an actuation strategy designed through finite element modeling to control its shape in terms of angle of attack and grasping radius. The presented soft finger exhibited a bending radius in the range of about 40 mm to 75 mm while simultaneously keeping the angle of attack around 90°. Different activations of the two-layer jamming modules also produced an alteration of the forces exerted by the finger which were characterized in terms of blocking and grasping force for different configurations. The results show an interesting and less explored use of variable stiffness, relevant for the development of adaptive soft grippers and manipulators. Moreover, the proposed concept and control strategy is independent of the actuation technologies used to produce finger bending.

I. INTRODUCTION

SOFT robotics is a rapidly growing field which aims at harnessing the mechanical properties of soft materials used in construction to solve open challenges of traditional robotics. Safe interaction with the environment and users, conformability, and exhibiting complex deformation with simple control are just a few of the capabilities enabled by the use of soft materials and which have been proved useful in several application scenarios, from extreme environment exploration [1] to the development of biomedical tools [2], robotic manipulators, and grippers [3]. In grasping tasks, replacing rigid joints and links with structures made of hyperelastic materials that deform continuously in response to actuation and through the interaction with objects, allows the grippers to naturally conform to different shapes, distribute the loads, and produce stable and delicate grasps also on deformable objects and for underactuated conceptual designs [4]. Soft grippers have been designed with many varying morphologies, dependent on the application for which they are required. There is a spectrum of morphologies with varying degrees of freedom. Finger based soft grippers offer large joint deformations extending the range of motion and ultimately seek to replicate the high dexterity of manipulation which is seen in the human hand [5]. Several

different actuation technologies have been used to develop soft robotics fingers, ranging from electro-active polymers and shape memory alloys to tendon-driven and pneumatic bending actuators [6]. Regardless of the technology, soft fingers present two intrinsic limitations: on one hand, the softer and more conformable they are, the lower are the forces that they can exert [7]; on the other, and this is especially true for underactuated designs, their morphology is bound to a single mode of deformation and additional systems are needed to adapt to different tasks [8]. The stiffness of the finger plays a crucial role in both cases as it is proportional to the amount of force that is exerted, and inversely proportional to the degree of deformation for a given force. Therefore, being able to actively modify the stiffness of the finger would enable the modulation of the forces exerted and provide control over its deformation. At the time of writing, an increment of the forces exerted has been demonstrated by integrating different variable stiffness (VS) technologies with various soft robotic fingers. In general, a stiffness variation can be obtained in three ways: stiffening by deformation, antagonistic activation and variation of intrinsic properties. The third option is gaining increasing attention, because it potentially provides higher compactness and it is decoupled from deformation [9]. Among the most recent/notable works on this topic, Wei et al. [10] integrated granular jamming in a pneumatic finger, Crowley et al. [11] presented the use of layer jamming in a pneumatic finger. Wang et al. described a shape memory alloy-based soft finger with two changeable stiffness hinges. In [12], a pneumatic finger actuator which uses low-melting-point alloys (LMPAs) as its variable stiffness layer is reported. On the other hand, the use of VS technologies for shape control capabilities has been less explored. In a recent work, Li et al. [13] proposed the integration of a fiber reinforced bending actuator with a total of two granular-jamming units acting as joints and three layer-jamming units subdividing the finger in as many links. The authors reported that different activations of the VS units resulted in different shapes of the finger and forces exerted and enabled the use of the finger for grasping objects of variable size. In this work, we aim at exploring the use of variable stiffness as a means of controlling the deformation of a soft robotic finger to implement an adaptive pinching grasp. Pinching is a widely used grasping mode, which consists in grasping an object using only the fingertips and keeping the angle of attack between the fingers and the objects as close as possible to 90° as shown in Fig. 1. Underactuated soft robotic fingers are not capable of pinching objects of different sizes because the position of the fingertip is coupled with their bending angle and thus, a specific angle of attack can

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Fig. 1: The ability of human hand to perform a variable size pinch grasp: angle of attack θ , grasping w width and h .

only be obtained for a fixed grasping width [14]. Similarly to the human fingers depicted in Fig. 1, the soft robotic finger hereby presented must be able to deform in configurations for which the fingertip is tangent to the object to be grasped for different grasping widths. To do so, we propose to augment the design of a Pneumatic Network (PneuNet) bending actuator using multiple independent Layer Jamming (LJ) modules and propose an actuation strategy designed through a finite element method (FEM) based model of the finger, to obtain the desired deformation. While the concept of variable kinematics enabled by variable stiffness is independent of the technology used in construction, in this work we have selected the PneuNet technology because of its widespread use in literature and the possibility to adapt its design to several application scenarios. Jamming transition was selected over other semiactive VS technologies [7] such as LMPAs or magnetic-driven systems because no heat or electromagnetic field is involved [15]. Among the different options available for jamming, namely granular, fiber and layer, the latter was selected because the stiffening mostly occurs along the longitudinal direction, higher stiffness increments were observed, and the units generally present a lower weight [16].

The contributions of this paper are the following:

- Present the design and fabrication of PneuNet based soft robotic finger, augmented with layer jamming modules to implement variable kinematics capability.
- Propose an actuation strategy for variable kinematics and use a FEM model of the finger to derive the actuation parameters.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In section II, we introduce the conceptual design of the finger and the actuation strategy for variable kinematics. We present a FEM model of the finger which includes the effect of VS, and use it to derive the control inputs for the actuation strategy. We introduce the experimental setup used for the characterization of the performance of the finger. In section III, we present and discuss the experimental results on the variable kinematics of the finger as well as on the blocking force and grasping force. Finally, in section IV, we draw our conclusions on the work.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Design and actuation strategy for variable kinematics

Unlike the human finger, the design of a continuous PneuNet bending actuator has just one way of bending and consequently, the fingertip follows a given trajectory on a 2D plane, in which its horizontal position is coupled with the bending angle [14]. To break this coupling, we propose the design shown in Fig. 2 featuring two PneuNets in series connected by a solid, non-inflatable link. The PneuNets receive pressurized air from the same source, and each PneuNet consists of three inflatable chambers. The inflatable chambers and air channel are sealed by a bottom layer which provides a mechanical constrain to promote planar bending of the structure and forces the bending direction inward. A similar design has been proposed in [17] as actuator in a rehabilitation glove and it is referred to as Segmented Pneumatic Bending Actuators (SPBA). In addition, the bottom layer of the finger integrates two LJ modules in the proximal and distal sections. Those modules can be independently activated and allow, upon the application of a negative relative pressure, to locally increase the stiffness of the bottom layer and block the deformation of the corresponding PneuNet. The design is completed by a solid structure in the proximal part of the finger with a groove to allow simple interlocking with a rigid attachment structure. The complete design of the finger and all relevant dimensions are shown in Fig. 2.

The soft robotic finger hereby presented has three inputs. The air input supplies positive pressure to the chambers of the SPBA and drives the deformation. The two vacuum inputs suck the air out of the LJ modules and stiffen them up. Previous studies on the vacuum based jamming transition [15] highlighted that the increase of stiffness primarily occurs when compliant layers are fully coupled. Consequently, LJ modules can be considered discrete and thus either be in an inactive compliant state, which allows the corresponding PneuNet to deform, or in an active stiff state, which blocks the deformation of the corresponding PneuNet. Finger configurations can be uniquely described by two variables. One option is considering the angles θ_1 and θ_2 , respectively corresponding to the bending angle of the distal and proximal PneuNet and defined in Fig. 3. This choice is directly linked to the actuation because θ_1 and θ_2 are function of pressure p supplied through the air input. A second option, consist in describing the position of the fingertip in a two dimensional cartesian space with configuration variables being the grasping width w and the grasping height h . Finally, considering the application of adaptive pinching grasp, it is natural to express the finger configuration using the grasping width w and the angle of attack $\theta = \theta_1 + \theta_2$. Under the assumption that the activation of each VS module perfectly blocks the corresponding segment and does not influence the deformation of the other, it is possible to evaluate each angular contribution separately and find the activation sequence that yields the desired finger configuration $\theta_1^{des} - \theta_2^{des}$. By defining p_1 as the pressure which brings $\theta_1 = \theta_1^{des}$ and p_2 as the pressure which brings $\theta_2 = \theta_2^{des}$, the sequential actuation strategy proposed comprises three steps and it is depicted in Fig. 3:

Fig. 2: Lateral and top section views of the soft actuator with the dimensions of relevant parameters.

- 1) Set air input to $\min(p_1, p_2)$. This action will bring the finger to an intermediate configuration $\theta_1^* - \theta_2^*$ in which only one of the two angles has reached the desired value.
- 2) Activate the VS module corresponding to the PneuNet which has reached the desired value. In other words, if $p_1 < p_2$ activate the proximal VS module, *else* activate the distal one.
- 3) Set air input to $\max(p_1, p_2)$. This action will bring the finger in the final configuration.

B. FEM Model

To assist the design of the presented actuator we have implemented a finite element model of the finger. The model has been developed with the Static Structural Analysis tool of ANSYS Workbench using the real dimensions of the finger reported in Fig. 2. Since modeling the jamming transition is outside of the scope of this work, the modules are modeled as homogeneous structures made of a fictitious linear elastic material that changes their stiffness with temperature. Hence, the changing temperature in the simulation has the only effect of varying the stiffness of the sections of the bottom layer corresponding to the LJ modules. In their active state, the elastic modulus of the jamming structure is set to the one of Polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and in their inactive state, the elastic modulus is reduced by a factor of n^2 , with $n = 20$ to match the experimental conditions [15]. The Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the PET layers are $E_s = 350$ GPa and 0.4, respectively. As boundary conditions, the finger is fixed

at one end, pressure is applied on the inner walls to simulate the air input, and the effect of the standard earth gravity is considered. The material used for the manufacturing of the finger is Dragon Skin 10-A silicone rubber. In simulation, it has been virtualized using a 3^{rd} order Yeoh model for hyperelastic, incompressible materials with the following strain energy function:

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^3 C_i (I_1 - 3)^i$$

where C_i are the material coefficients and the I_1 the first strain invariant. The coefficients were identified by fitting the model to the experimental data obtained through standard uniaxial tensile tests (ASTM D142) at a rate of 200 mm/min and resulted to be $C_1 = 3.8323$, $C_2 = -0.10358$ and $C_3 = 0.01914$ MPa. The model hereby presented has been used to evaluate the finger's forward kinematics, i.e. the relation between the air input p and the configuration angles θ_1 and θ_2 in absence of VS activation. This allows to evaluate the values of p_1 and p_2 and which VS segment is necessary to activate according to the proposed actuation strategy. Then, FEM simulations are conducted to estimate the bending behavior of the actuator. Moreover, a blocking force test is implemented to evaluate the effect of the stiffness performance of the actuator on the finger. The value of the blocking force is investigated in three different conditions:

- no activation of LJ modules;
- activation of LJ proximal module;
- activation of LJ distal module.

C. Fabrication

The manufacturing of the finger consists of a multi-step open moulding procedure. The moulds have been designed using SolidWorks and 3D-printed using a ProJet MJP 3600 from 3D Systems. The two reagents of the Dragon Skin 10A silicone rubber have been mixed in equal parts, de-gassed in a vacuum oven, and poured in the moulds for the upper and bottom layer. The parts are cured at room temperature and demolded. In parallel, 0.12 mm thickness layers of PET are cut using a laser cutting machine (Universal Laser XLS10MWH, Universal225, Laser System Inc., US) and inserted into two dedicated pouches cut out of the bottom layer. Each pouch is

Fig. 3: Definition of the angles θ_1 and θ_2 , grasping radius r and height h . Schematic representation of the actuation strategy in the case $p_1 < p_2$.

filled with 20 layers and sealed with uncured silicone. Finally, the upper and bottom parts are joined using a small quantity of uncured silicone and inserting the pipe for the air and vacuum inputs.

D. Variable kinematics test

To validate our design and actuation strategy, we have developed an experimental setup to measure the bending behaviour of the finger for different actuation sequences. The finger has been mounted on a platform with a 3D-printed fixture and an HD camera is used to capture the finger's planar bending motion. For the fluidic actuation of the air input, the pressure has been controlled by a proportional pressure regulator (K8P-0-D522-0, Camozzi Group) directly connected to an air compressor (Leonardo 101, FIAC S.p.A.). For driving the LJ modules, we have implemented a simple on/off control on a vacuum pump (Oil Lubricated Rotary Vane Pumps MM56p2, D.V.P Vacuum Technology s.r.l., 260 Carpanelli S.p.A.). The negative pressure necessary to set the LJ modules in an active state, measured by an absolute pressure sensor (SWCN-V01-P3-2, Camozzi Group), corresponds to 0.1 bar, whereas the pressure to set the LJ module in an inactive state corresponds to the ambient pressure. Six different actuation sequences have been tested and recorded. The angle of attack θ , the grasping radius w and the grasping height h at the equilibrium position were manually extracted.

E. Blocking force and grasping force tests

Although in this work the primary role of VS is to enable variable kinematics on an underactuated soft finger, the stiffness variations for different actuation sequences are likely to influence also the amount of force that finger can exert on the environment. To measure this effect, we have developed two experimental setups to implement a blocking force test and a grasping force test. As far as the actuation for the air and vacuum inputs are concerned, the same equipment described in the previous paragraph has been used. The experimental setup for the blocking force tests consists in attaching the proximal end of the actuator horizontally with the fingertip above a 6-axis load cell (ATI Industrial Automation, USA) as depicted in Fig. 4. The experimental protocol consists in pressurizing the finger up to 0.4 bar with steps of 0.1 bar for three conditions, namely both VS modules OFF, VS distal module ON, and VS proximal module ON, and recording the force measurements from the load cell. The tests have been repeated three times for each pressure value and VS activation, and compared with the results obtained with the FEM model under the same conditions.

The experimental setup for the grasping force test is depicted in Fig. 5. We are referring to this test as 'grasping force' because, unlike the blocking force test, it aims at measuring the force exerted by the finger in configurations which resemble a grasping application. The finger is attached horizontally from the proximal end, and the load cell is mounted on a 3D-printed sliding support to change its position according to the different finger configurations that will be tested. The experimental protocol consists in actuating the finger using the same six

Fig. 4: Experimental setup for measuring the blocking force F_{block} . Finger at 0.2 bar with no VS activation is shown.

configurations used for the variable kinematics tests. Once the finger has reached the equilibrium position, the load cell is moved next to the fingertip and the grasping force is measured for air input pressures equal to 0.3 and 0.4 bar. Three trials were executed for each pressure and the mean grasping force was computed for each configuration of the finger.

Fig. 5: Experimental setup for measuring the grasping force F_{grasp} for a given configuration.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Variable kinematics

The FEM model described in the previous section was used to retrieve the relation between $\theta_1 - \theta_2$ and the air input p to be used in the implementation of the proposed actuation strategy for variable kinematics. The relations were derived for the case of both VS modules inactive and are plotted in Fig. 6. The two curves follow similar paths, with an almost linear behaviour for low values of p and a steeper region starting from $p = 0.25$ bar. The effect of gravity on the two angles can be clearly observed from Fig. 6, with the proximal angle θ_1 being always greater than the distal one θ_2 due to the weight of the distal part of the finger.

Based on the relations of Fig. 6, we have identified 16 couples (p_1, p_2) for which the corresponding θ_1 and θ_2 sum to 90° . The value of 90° was selected because the finger is meant to be used for pinching grasp, however, the same procedure can be applied for different angles depending on

Fig. 6: FEM relation between θ_1 and θ_2 and the input pressure with an example of identification of p_1 and p_2 in the case of $\theta = 90^\circ$

the application. Prior to experimental tests, we tested the proposed actuation strategy on the FE model using the six combinations introduced above. The resulting grasping width w and height h as functions of θ_1 and θ_2 are reported in Fig. 7a-b. In particular, we can observe that the proposed actuation strategy allowed to reach w in the range between 40 to 80 mm, while keeping h in a smaller range of 60 to 75 mm. As expected, most of the greater grasping widths (60 to 80 mm) were obtained for configurations in which the proximal module is activated (corresponding to blue-circled spheres in Fig. 7a).

The average angle of attack $\theta = \theta_1 + \theta_2$ resulting from the FE model is 88.59° with a standard deviation of 11.21° . By looking at the $\theta_1\theta_2$ plane in Fig. 7c it is clear that only a few configurations resulted in the desired $\theta = 90^\circ$ with the majority falling in the range $[70 - 110]^\circ$. These results are partially in contrast with the initial hypothesis, under which the relations between θ_1 , θ_2 , and p were derived, according to which the activation of layer jamming units would completely block the corresponding section and not influence the other. A possible explanation for these results is that the PneuNet corresponding to the inactive VS module experiences a higher pressure than expected due to the impossibility of the chambers of the other blocked PneuNet to fully inflate.

The same results can be observed in Fig. 8 which shows the bending behavior of the simulated and physical finger for six actuation sequences and report the resulting values of w , h , and θ . Configurations a-c have been obtained by activating the LJ distal module, whereas configurations d-f have been obtained by activating the proximal one. The configurations are arranged from left to right with increasing values of grasping range w . Visually, it can be observed that as w increases, θ_1 is decreasing and θ_2 is increasing. From the results presented in Fig. 8, we can also state that the FEM model predicts well the deformation of the finger. Indeed the grasping width and height were predicted with a maximum error of 6 ± 5 and 6 ± 3 mm respectively, corresponding to

relative 6 % to the total length of the finger. In terms of θ , FEM results show a good comparison with a maximum error of $12 \pm 5^\circ$. In particular, the assumption that an active LJ module perfectly blocks the corresponding PneuNet does not hold. This can be observed for configurations a-c, for which the model slightly underestimates θ and overestimates w ; as well as for configurations d-f, for which both θ and w are overestimated by the model. Indeed, in the prototype, a partial slippage or movement of the layers, neglected in FE simulations, may occur and cause the corresponding segment to deform.

B. Blocking and grasping force

The results of blocking force tests are reported in Fig. 9 together with the blocking force obtained in simulation. As expected, regardless of the activation of VS modules, the blocking force measured by the load cell increases with increasing values of air input pressure. A good correspondence is observed between simulations and experimental data, with the former slightly overestimating the latter. In experimental conditions, when both LJ modules are inactive, the finger can exert a maximum blocking force F_{max} of 0.54 ± 0.07 N at 0.4 bar. The activation of the LJ distal module causes the blocking force to increase up to 0.75 ± 0.05 N at 0.4 bar. The higher results in terms of blocking force have been obtained by activating the proximal LJ module and leaving the distal off. In this case, the maximum blocking force measured by the load cell is 0.94 ± 0.12 N at 0.4 bar, with a percentage increase of 74% with respect to the case of no active LJ module. The fact that a higher blocking force is measured when the proximal LJ model is active with respect to when the distal LJ module is active was expected as a stiffer proximal section of the finger allows most of the force to be transmitted close to the point of contact with the load cell.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

Soft bending actuators present a single mode of deformation which is bound to their geometry and material properties. Moreover, a trade-off must be found between their compliance, which yields safety and conformability, and their ability to exert adequate forces for their task. Both issues can be related to stiffness which is inversely proportional to the amount of deformation for a given actuation level and directly proportional to the forces exerted. At present, most works focus on the integration of VS mechanisms for augmenting the output force that the finger may exert. In this work, instead, we have focused on the use of VS to control the kinematics of a soft finger in order to adapt to different shapes in pinching grasps. We have presented a novel bending actuator in which variable kinematics is enabled by the presence of VS mechanism and proposed an actuation strategy based on FEM analysis to obtain the desired shape in terms of angle of attack θ and grasping width w . Our experimental results confirmed the ability to control the shape of the presented actuator and obtain w in the range 40 – 75 mm while keeping θ as close as possible to 90° . Additionally, we have characterized the increment in blocking force and grasping force yielded by the

Fig. 7: FEM: configurations of the bending actuator for pinching grasp. Relation between a) θ and w , b) θ and h , c) θ_1 θ_2 .

Fig. 8: Comparison between FEM and experimental results of the bending behaviour of the actuator. In particular, r [mm], h [mm], θ [°] are reported.

TABLE I: Values of F_{grasp} for the six grasping widths w at 0.3 and 0.4 bar input pressure p .

p [bar] \ r [mm]	a) 40	b) 47	c) 54	d) 61	d) 65	f) 70
0.3	0.65 ± 0.07	0.69 ± 0.07	0.69 ± 0.09	0.83 ± 0.10	0.90 ± 0.11	0.91 ± 0.09
0.4	0.79 ± 0.09	0.98 ± 0.10	0.92 ± 0.08	1.11 ± 0.12	1.31 ± 0.08	1.23 ± 0.12

activation of LJ modules in different configurations. In this work, variable kinematics was demonstrated by embedding two LJ modules in the bottom layer of an SPBA and targeting $\theta = 90^\circ$ for pinching applications. In particular, this research was carried out in the framework of the European research project SoftGrip. This novel bending actuator may be applied to the mushroom harvesting industry. Indeed, the proposed finger may allow the implementation of a grasping strategy consisting of pinching the mushroom cap with the fingertips to minimize the contact area as done by human harvesters to

avoid undesired blemishing/bruising and aiming at minimizing the vertical component of the grasping force that may cause the detachment of the cap from the stem of the mushroom. However, the concept of enabling variable kinematics through VS mechanism is independent of this particular implementation and can be replicated with different actuation technologies. In future studies, the dimensions of the jamming modules and the number of layers will be optimized to improve the finger's performance and soft bending sensors will be integrated into the correspondence of the two LJ modules to obtain feedback

Fig. 9: Comparison between FEM and experimental results of the blocking force. Dashed lines represent FEM simulations, and solid lines represent experimental data.

on θ_1 and θ_2 and implement a closed-loop control strategy. Finally, the fingers will be integrated into a gripper to exploit the variable kinematics capability demonstrated in grasping tasks.

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